

Ethno-religious Violence in Pakistan: A Study of *Ice-Candy Man* and *Meatless Days*

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 02, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Colonialism, Nationalism, Neo- colonialism, Ethnicity, Islamization.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5120942</p>	<p><i>According to Frantz Fanon, the third world countries face problem of ethno-religious violence. Pakistan is one of such post-colonial countries. This issue has been depicted by several literary writers such as Bapsi Sidhwa and Sara Suleri. The research paper analyzes the problem of ethno-religious rivalries in Pakistan. The Indian subcontinent was divided into Pakistan and India in 1947. However, the separation of East Pakistan (Bangladesh) in 1971 due to ethnic politics has raised serious concerns about national identity. The paper aims to answer the most important question as to why Pakistan faces problems of ethno-religious violence after the partition of the United India. In the third-world countries, the ruling elites exploit people on the basis of ethnicity and religion. It results in eruption of ethnic and religious violence in the country. Fanon's views about neocolonialism are relevant in this context. The study is based on textual analysis (based on interpretation of selected passages) of a novel <i>Ice-Candy Man</i> and a memoir, <i>Meatless Days</i>. The study is significant in highlighting the problems of ethnic politics and religious violence in Pakistan. There is a need of minimizing religious chauvinism and ethnic politics in Pakistan.</i></p>

Introduction

This paper addresses the problem of ethnic and religious violence in Pakistan. Pakistan got independence in the name of Muslim nationhood, an idea which was strengthened with Islamic ideology. Muslim nationhood was the telos and vision of the movement of liberation. However, the country after partition, became victim of ethnic and sectarian differences which shattered the vision of Muslim unity.

Pakistani fiction in English (the first-generation fiction writers) addresses the issues of partition, Islamization and ethnicity. Abdullah Hussein's *The Weary Generations*, Intizar Hussain's *Basti*, Bapsi Sidhwa's *Ice-Candy Man*, and Sara Suleri's *Meatless Days* are few of them. These writers depict partition of the subcontinent with particular focus on the miserable and traumatic experiences of the migrants during the partition and the subsequent disappointment due to ethnic and religious marginalization after the partition, "first-generation writers tend to focus ... on the tragic aftermath of the Indo-Pak Partition and post-independence social realities" (Kanwal, 2015, p. 21). The present paper analyzes *Ice-Candy Man* and *Meatless days* with the intention to delve into the issues of ethnic and religious violence in Pakistan, a post-colonial country which promised unity on the basis of religious identity.

Nationalism can best be understood in entirety in the context of colonization since nationalist movements emerged in reaction to oppressive policies of colonization. Colonization served as a catalyst in motivating the freedom movements against the colonizers. Nationalism promised the colonized a land of their own in which they could attain status of equality. These movements inspired the colonized to win freedom for themselves though many newly independent nation-states in the post-colonial world remain under control of dictators; Sara Suleri's memoir, *Meatless Days*, depicts one such post-colonial country, highlights creation of Pakistan and the subsequent military dictatorship which led to political disintegration of East Pakistan in 1971.

Pakistan like other post-colonial countries has a history of colonization and faces problems of ethnic exploitation through ethnic politics. Akbar S. Ahmed (1997) comments on the same situation in Pakistan in the following words:

The emergence of new classes, new political and social elites, and the clash of languages and cultures were reflected in politics and found ethnic expression.

In East Pakistan this rapidly formed around the idea of a West Pakistani elite bullying and exploiting its eastern wing. In particular, Punjabi officials were accused of being almost neo-colonialist in their attitudes. (p. 211)

Politics based on ethnic identity is practiced in South Asia where "ethnic and religious violence" (Nandy 2002, p. 4) create rifts among people of the same nation. Minorities become victims of communal violence due to their

ethnicity. It was ethnic prejudice against Bengalis of East Pakistan which led to separation of Bangladesh in 1971. Separation of East Pakistan constitutes the recurring theme of *Meatless Days* which foregrounds the creation of Pakistan on the basis of religious identity and the war of 1971 which resulted in separation of East Pakistan.

As already said, *Ice-Candy Man* and *Meatless Days* reflect on the themes of decolonization of British Colonial Raj and separation of East Pakistan from West Pakistan, it is important to discuss first *Ice-Candy Man* since it depicts precolonial India wherein characters of diverse beliefs lived in perfect harmony, oblivious of the differences which during the partition promoted feelings of hatred.

Partition of the United India and Religious Identities

The partition of Indian subcontinent in 1947 as a result of decolonization of the British Colonial Raj led to emergence of “ethnonational oppression” (Cocks,2002, p. 54) in the post-colonial countries, India and Pakistan. The idea of ethnicity during partition of the United India proved to be a bloody one. It caused killing of millions of people who belonged to various religious groups such as Muslims, Hindus, Sikhs, Parsees etc. Bapsi Sidhwa wrote *Ice-Candy Man* about the trauma caused by faith-based partition of the United India. The novel unfolds story of the trauma of characters during the partition. It addresses the issues of nationalism and the resulting identities which led people of the Indian subcontinent into the dark abyss of ethnic and religious hatred. The novel narrates “the widespread bloodshed, raping, looting, and arson amongst Muslims, Sikhs, and Hindus...the massacre of at least one million crossing in both directions over new national borders” (Hai,2000, p. 387). In this section, I will focus on the reasons which disturbed the environment of harmony and mutual trust.

The story of *Ice-Candy Man* is narrated by a Parsee girl, polio victim, named Lenny. The choice of Lenny is important because Sidhwa looks at the partition through the lens of Lenny who belonged to the minority community of Parsees, “In the novel’s account, Parsis or Zoroastrians were politically neutral in a conflict whose central agents were Hindus, Muslims and Sikhs” (Daiya,2008, p. 68). Lenny narrates the violent situation which emerged during the days of partition, a situation that was friendly and peaceful till then. She also observes the plight of her maid, Ayah, who suffered due to the partition motivated by religious identity. The novel is important not only for the theme of partition but also for the status of minority in the post-colonial countries which emerged on the basis of religious identity.

In the novel, the characters who belonged to various religious groups such as Sikhs, Hindus and Muslims, lived in a peaceful environment before the partition. They supported each other, ignored their religious differences and showed unity against the British colonizers, “Hindu, Muslim, Sikh: we all want the same thing! We want independence!” (Sidhwa, 2015,p. 63). Their feelings of affinity became even stronger in showing resistance against the British colonizers. Various characters of different religious backgrounds lived together in harmony and were united against the British colonizers; it shows their firm belief in the United India wherein they could live peacefully without letting religious differences spoil their harmony. Hindus and Muslims strived on political level for achieving independence from the British Raj. In the novel, the characters of diverse religious backgrounds show a strong conviction in brotherhood, a key feature of harmony among the characters of richly diverse religious backgrounds in the Indian subcontinent. Jagjeet Singh, a Sikh *granthi* (priest) says, “Our villages come from the same racial stock. Muslim or Sikh, we are basically *Jats*. We are brothers. How can we fight each other?” (Sidhwa, 2015,p. 57). The claim of affinity is supported by a Muslim *chaudhry*, “To us villagers, what does it matter if a peasant is a Hindu, or a Muslim, or a Sikh?” (p. 57). Their bond of affinity was so strong that they never imagined being hostile to each other. When Sher Singh asks Ice-Candy Man that why a Muslim will help a Sikh, Ice-Candy Man responds to him, “So what if you are a Sikh? I am first a friend to my friends... And an enemy to their enemies...And then a Mussulman!” (p. 124). Muslims, Sikhs, Parsees and Hindus had no problem in sitting together; they lived peacefully.

The unity of Muslims and Hindus was seen during their political campaigns. Muslims and Hindus came closer during *Khilafat Movement*; it diminished role of All India Muslim League, (Jalal, 2014,p. 20). This unity of the Muslims and Hindus could not continue after Mustapha Kamal Pasha announced abolition of the caliphate in 1924. The Hindu-Muslim unity, an ideal wish of the Indians, lost its fascination after the collapse of the *Khilafat Movement*. The British favored the resulting situation of growing differences, (p. 20). Sidhwa also depicts the strategy of the British to divide the Indians. The Government House gardener says, “It is the English’s mischief...They are past masters at intrigue. It suits them to have us all fight” (Sidhwa, 2015,p. 93). The novel highlights violence caused by the partition which promoted hostilities among Indians on the basis of national identities (Hai, 2000,p. 388).

Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah was supported by the Muslims, “Jinnah has the backing of seventy million Indian Muslims!” (Sidhwa, 2015, p. 64). These Muslims “want(ed) the Muslim majority provinces: Punjab, Sind, Kashmir, the North West and Bengal” (Sidhwa, 2015, p.64). However, the Muslim League was not supported by all the Muslims in the partition on the basis of the above mentioned plan; there were certain political groups which opposed The Muslim League (Azad, 2011, p.245). One such political group known as the *Khudai Khidmatgar* (Servants of God) in NWFP has been mentioned nowhere in the novel. This

political group was led by Abdul Ghaffar Khan. He supported sovereignty of Pathans or Pakhtuns and wanted to lead them under leadership of the Congress (Jalal, 2014, p.17). The claim of The Muslim League being supported by all Indian-Muslims also failed during the partition after which most of the Muslims remained in India. This claim of Muslim brotherhood was further proven to be weak when Bengal (East Pakistan), which constituted majority, separated from Pakistan (West Pakistan) in 1971.

About the Indian political leaders who, during the partition, created rift in the unity of various ethnic and religious groups living in the United India, Ayah says, "What is it to us if Jinnah, Nehru and Patel fight? They are not fighting our fight." (Sidhwa, 2015, p. 77). Sharbat Khan supported her view, "They are stirring up trouble for us all." (p. 77). The trauma of partition is ascribed to the Indian political leaders who could not maintain unity against the British Raj; they divided on the basis of their religious creeds. Thus Sharbat Khan's prediction of trouble proved to be true because massacre and bloodshed became fate of the partition. Growing sensitivity toward religious differences took Hindus and Muslims far away from each other. Ayah after the partition suffered loss of her dignity and respect due to being Hindu.

In the wake of their religious differences due to the partition of the Indian subcontinent, their peaceful life turned into one of extreme hostility and bloodshed. The city of Lahore witnessed violence during the partition which forced non-Muslims to migrate from Lahore (Daiya, 2008, p. 68). The narrator, Lenny, says, "And I become aware of religious differences. It is sudden. One day everybody is themselves- and the next day they are Hindu, Muslim, Sikh, Christian. People shrink, dwindling into symbols" (Sidhwa, 2015, p. 94). Religious differences ignited flames of fire and people burnt in the flames of differences, "He [Dost Mohammad] tells the villagers that the Sikhs have attacked at least five villages... They are killing all Muslims. Setting fires, looting, parading the Muslim women naked through the streets- raping and mutilating them in the center of villages and in mosques" (p. 202). This proves to be a turning point in the history of the Indian subcontinent which witnessed decline in ethnic and religious solidarity, and was threatened due to religious differences after demise of the British Raj. People turned into brutes when they became conscious about their religious identities. Their spirit of tolerance evaporated when the clouds of religious identity hovered over them. Master Tara Singh says in a furious manner that he will not let the Muslims get their separate country, Pakistan (Sidhwa, 2015, pp. 136-137). They were no more friends; their friendship turned into enmity and they did not hesitate in killing each other, (p. 202). Thus the Partition of the United India created a situation of genocide. Religious identity engulfed Pakistan and India in never-ending religious hatred. The partition created problems for the people living in their native places since they were no more to be treated as respectable citizens due to their minority status (Daiya, 2008, p. 71). Driven by religious identities, the characters changed their loyalties; they developed friendship or attachment on the basis of religious identity. Hary/Himat Ali embraces Islam when Muslim men search him, Imam Din tells them, "Hari-the-gardener has become Himat Ali!" (Sidhwa, 2015, p.185). The Muslim men are not satisfied and thus want to confirm his circumcision. He is not harmed because he recites the Kalma (Islamic), "with the cadence and intonation of Hindu chants" (pp. 185-186).

The character of Ayah, a maid of Lenny, is significant since she became a victim to the faith-based partition. Before the partition, she was admired by various characters including Muslims, Sikhs and Hindus. Lenny says that "I learn also to detect the subtle exchange of signals and some of the complex rites by which Ayah's admirers co-exist" (Sidhwa, 2015, p.19). She was very friendly with all the people irrespective of their ethnicities, "Only the group around Ayah remains unchanged. Hindu, Muslim, Sikh, Parsee are, as always, unified around her" (p. 98). She had close romantic attachment to Ice-Candy Man. But sensitivity about religious identity soon prevailed and it created differences among people of different faith (Daiya, 2008, p. 68). Lenny, the narrator, says, "Ayah is no longer just my all-encompassing Ayah-she is also a token. A Hindu." (Sidhwa, 2015, p. 94). Ayah became victim to the cultural and ethnic traumas which occurred during the partition of the Indian subcontinent. After the partition, she faced a tragic life: she was abducted and became "a dancing girl" (p. 245). The partition motivated by religious identity humiliated her. She did not want to live in the newly-born country, Pakistan (p. 266). She wanted to leave Pakistan for Amritsar because her lover, Ice-Candy Man, humiliated her, "When I [Lenny] think of Ayah I think she must get away from the monster [Ice-Candy Man] who has killed her spirit and mutilated her angel's voice" (p. 269). The miserable life of Ayah, Hindu, reveals an important fact about the rights of minorities living in Pakistan. The romantic relationship of Ice-Candy Man and Ayah shattered by the partition, reveals the horror of religious differences which sensitized differences among religious groups. It also symbolizes the insecure position of minorities after the partition both in Pakistan and India. Her miserable fate affirms doubts of Hannah Arendt, a German-American philosopher and political theorist, who thinks that, "The domination of a minority people by a national majority is as unfortunate as the minority's acquisition of its own separate nation-state, with the domination of some new minority as the result" (as cited in Cocks, 2002, p. 61). Ayah was dominated by the Muslim majority and victimized due to her status of minority. The status of minority gained importance especially after the partition which was motivated by religious identity. Lenny as a narrator foregrounds sufferings and victimization of Ayah who represents all the minorities in the subcontinent (Kanwal, 2015, p. 22). After the partition of the

subcontinent, religion has become the foremost factor in the shaping of identity. The subcontinent was divided into two countries, India and Pakistan. This division resulted in the homelands of Hindus and Muslims. However, it threw away other religious communities such as Sikhs and Parsees into the distant orbits of the new nation-states; they felt themselves alienated due to the partition which was based on religious ideology. Lenny unveils her anguish about her marginalized identity, “The Sikh women pull me to their laps and ask my name and the name of my religion. ‘I’m Parsee,’ I say. ‘O Kee? What is that?’ they ask: scandalized to discover a religion they have never heard of (Sidhwa, 2015, p. 98). Paromita Deb (2011) comments on the status of Parsees that the novel depicts suffering of the marginalized status of the minority (Parsees) who were not considered during the partition (p. 218).

The partition added to the confusion and miseries of Lenny who was Parsee. The miserable situation during the partition is focalized through her eyes. She “provides a non-dominant Parsi perspective on the Indo-Pak Partition” (Kanwal, 2015, p.22). Being a child narrator, she narrates the story without any malice or racial discrimination. The Indian Subcontinent was divided into Muslims and Hindus; she belonged to none of the two groups. She anticipated her marginalized status even after partition. The fear of insecure position of Parsees in a country of Muslim/Hindu majority is supported by the view of Henna Arendt, who is of the view that decolonization leads to the colonization of new minority groups. The partition of the Indian subcontinent created a new phase of trial for the minorities such as Parsees in the newly independent countries wherein they had to develop a new relationship with new people in a new country which came into being on the basis of religious identity. Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah gave his vision of security to minorities in Pakistan, “our own history and our Prophet have given the clearest proof that non-Muslims have been treated not only justly and fairly but generously” (Ahmed, 1997, p. 195). He was determined to give protection to the non-Muslims in Pakistan. However, it remained just a promise which has not yet been materialized. The minorities in Pakistan feel themselves alienated. The marginalized status of the minority groups such as Parsees is depicted through narration of Lenny in the novel (Deb, 2011, p. 219). The fear of insecurity of Parsees during General Zia’s Islamization is depicted in Sidhwa’s novel *An American Brat*. General Zia’s reign of Islamization is the most conspicuous example of religious chauvinism.

Sidhwa (2015) makes the fact evident that sensitizing religious differences leads only to hatred and violence, “One man’s religion is another man’s poison” (p.118). This is one of the factors responsible for bloodshed during the partition of the Subcontinent. Such sensitivity towards religious differences created problems after decolonization. People of the same religion develop consciousness about sectarian differences. Fanon (2004) has discussed the issue of differences which develop in the same nation in the name of ethnicity and sects, “Within the same nation, religion divides the people and sets the spiritual communities, fostered and encouraged by colonialism and its apparatus, at odds with each other” (p. 107). The partition of the subcontinent in the name of ethnicities has resulted in grave problems such as “ethnic and religious violence ... in South Asia” (Nandy, 2002, p. 4). The differences based on ethnicities have created hatred for each other. Due to religious identity, interfaith harmony among various ethnic groups has vanished. Intolerance prevails both in India and Pakistan. The rise of religious zeal makes a person very rigid, which leads to zero tolerance for other sectarian/religious groups.

The same Muslim nation of Pakistan experienced the pangs of sectarian differences. The sectarian differences are reflected in various sects such as Sunni, Shi’a, Barelvi etc, live. Sunni Muslims constitute a major part of Muslims in Pakistan. Sectarian violence has disturbed peaceful environment in the country. The conflict between Sunni and Shi’a Muslims is part of the violence (Ahmed, 1997, p. 188). Due to internal differences, it seems to be difficult to materialize the dream of a nation based on Muslim brotherhood. These differences do not let harmony develop among Muslims. This is the reason that violence due to sectarian differences is witnessed in Pakistan.

Politics based on ethnicity is yet another factor which has disturbed national brotherhood, and is prevalent in Pakistan, “Because of the failure to develop a ‘Pakistani’ national identity, ethnic and tribal identities remain strong” (Ahmed, 1997, p. 188). It has caused much damage to solidarity of the country. Pakistan witnessed political disintegration due to marginalization of the Muslims of East Pakistan on the basis of ethnicity. Ethnic politics leading to separation of East Pakistan (Bangladesh) is portrayed in Suleri’s memoir, *Meatless Days*.

Military Elites and Ethnic Politics in Pakistan

The memoir *Meatless Days* of Sara Suleri is included in the paper because it focuses on the role of military elites and ethnic politics in Pakistan. Though it is a memoir, however it is not Suleri who defines herself in it. Shazia Rahman comments on it, “Suleri’s life story cannot be read except in relation to the stories of others in her life. [...] We are led to believe that others define her” (as cited in Ghosh, 2019, p.5). Oliver Lovesey also comments on the role of Suleri in the memoir, “*Meatless Days* constructs postcolonial subjectivity almost exclusively by talking about other people; Suleri is not her tale’s protagonist” (as cited in Ghosh, 2019, p. 5). This technique of portrayal makes the memoir suitable for the study.

The memoir is mainly about the marginalized women in Pakistan, “there are no women in the third world” (Suleri, 2015, p.20). Suleri depicts the silenced community of women skillfully by focusing on her family members. Ray (1993) refers to it by saying that Suleri narrates story of her family during the partition which reconstructed the nation of Pakistan (p. 49). Suleri depicts violation of her family members (Begums) who buy enough meat for the meatless days (Suleri, 2015, pp. 31-32). The rich class [Begums] can afford storage of meat on meatless days. The title of the memoir *Meatless Days* refers to the government’s announcement of two-day ban in a week “in order to conserve the national supply of goats and cattle” (p. 31). The government shows ineptitude in implementing its own announcement of the ban. It reveals that Pakistani society is based on stratification which confirms the imagined status of Pakistani nation i.e. their national brotherhood is claimed on the imagined community.

Suleri(2015) also depicts the history of Pakistan’s independence which witnessed violence and trauma. She unveils disappointment of her Dadi who does not show any excitement on independence day (p. 2) since the partition on the basis of religious identity witnessed atrocities and bloodshed.

It also portrays Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto’s era which was disrupted by the Islamization of General Zia who exploited religion for prolonging his military rule. This was a turbulent phase because it led to the decline of Muslim nationhood due to the separation of East Pakistan (Bangladesh). Suleri unveils disappointment of the active supporters who struggled for an independent state because they witnessed political and ethnic marginalization in the country which resulted in separation of East Pakistan (Bangladesh) in 1971.

Suleri portrays horrors of the partition which created new problems after decolonization. Their frustration can be ascribed partly to the unexpected division of the United India on the basis of religion and partly to the bloodshed and massacre which occurred during the partition. Suleri(2015) depicts the panic and trauma created due to killing of the innocent people during the partition of the Subcontinent (p. 116). The partition divided the United India into Muslims and Hindus; they had to leave their native lands. It was not easy to leave one’s native land to which their families were rooted. However, the Muslims who opted for Pakistan, entered into a new phase of traumatic life. The dream of Pakistan’s independence gave unparalleled excitement to the new nation but their jubilation could not continue for a long time. It was trampled due to the vested interests of the elites and resulted in social and political inequalities which promoted differences and deprivation. Consequently, the tragic war of 1971 led to the separation of Muslims in East Pakistan. Pakistan could not maintain national unity which was a motivating factor in the separation of Pakistan. Secession of the East Pakistan [now known as Bangladesh] is an evidence of it, “when East Pakistan became Bangladesh and Indira Gandhi hailed the demise of the two-nation theory” (Suleri, 2015, p. 8). The partition of Bangladesh occurred due to “a deathly power struggle between Bhutto and Mujeeb” (p. 20).

Post-colonial countries have witnessed power struggle due to which the political leaders have deviated from the aim of serving their people. The slogans which motivated resistance to colonialism, lost their spirit after decolonization. The newly independent nation saw rise of the national bourgeoisie which, after independence, turned away from the national aspirations of its people, “...that the national bourgeoisie often turns away from this heroic and positive path, which is both productive and just, and unabashedly opts for the anti-national, and therefore abhorrent, path of a conventional bourgeoisie, a bourgeois that is dismally, inanely, and cynically bourgeoisie” (Fanon, 2004, p. 99). The national bourgeoisie did not materialize dreams of its people; it did not promote interests of its people. The powerstruggle between Bhutto and Mujeeb is an example of it. Their conflict confirms Fanon’s criticism of post-independent situation, “it is simply a power struggle” (p. 23). Mujeeb was the elected leader of East Pakistan while Bhutto of West Pakistan. People of East Pakistan felt themselves alienated and marginalized and thus they revolted. Fanon (2004) expresses his view about marginalization of certain ethnic groups after independence, “The cracks in it explain how easy it is for young independent countries to switch back from nation to ethnic group and from state to tribe- a regression which is so terribly detrimental and prejudicial to the development of the nation and national unity” (p.97).

Ethnic differences emerge due to national bourgeoisie’s utilization of power discriminately. It deprives people of their rights; it does not materialize their dreams which they have aspired during their struggle of liberation. It leads to the crumbling of national reality. Regionalism develops in such a situation since the national bourgeoisie is incapable of maintaining national unity. The people who live in the prosperous regions, ignore underprivileged people of the nation. It creates a gap between the prosperous class and the miserable people. Different ethnic groups start fight for securing interests which promotes hatred and differences among people of the same nation. Thus national unity loses its spirit due to the ‘mask of neocolonialism’ (Fanon, 2004, p. 101) of the national bourgeoisie in the third world countries. In Pakistan, the national bourgeoisie is supported by military elites in order to support their military control through controlled democracy or military dictatorship.

After the partition, Pakistani nation was dominated by the military dictators such as General Ayub, General Yahya and then General Zia UIHaq. During the rule of General Zia:

Laws were changing in Pakistan, and I [Suleri] had a dread that the country was prepared to consume the last vestiges of its compassion ... Bhutto had been hanged...I could feel that a brute energy was

building up in Pakistan, as though the ghost of that populace –mercilessly cast about in 1947, then again in 1971-had summoned up its strength again... (Suleri, 2014, p. 125)

Islamization during the reign of General Zia is of prime importance in the memoir. Pakistan came into being on the basis of ideology of Islam. Islamic ideology is thus the most important feature of this state. Religious zeal was a catalyst in the freedom movement and it still prevails in the country. However, the element of religion could not unite Muslims of Pakistan, “I [Suleri] think we dimly knew we were about to witness Islam’s departure from the land of Pakistan. The men would take it to the streets and make it vociferous, but the great romance between religion and the populace, the embrace that engendered Pakistan, was done” (p. 15). The war of 1971 has proved the fact that the partition of the Indian Subcontinent on the basis of religion could not unite the people; religion could not prove itself as a strong bond to give a collective identity in order to unite them. Mostly religious zeal of Pakistani Muslims was exploited by the political and military elites. Dynastic politics and military dictatorship in Pakistan have pushed ideology into the background. General Zia is an example of military elite since he prolonged his military dictatorship in the name of Islam.

General Zia’s ambition for Islamization was motivated by prolonging his military dictatorship. It is a known fact that Pakistan separated as a nation of Muslims; Islam was the basis of its ideology. During the movement of freedom in the Subcontinent, Islam was the driving force of the unity of Muslims. Many religious parties still exist in the country but they have not secured status of the mainstream political parties. Islamization is exploited for political purposes and the best example is military dictatorship of Zia Ul-Haq who extended his rule in Pakistan in the name of Islamization (Suleri, 2014, p.17). Military dictatorship of General Zia disrupted the democratic government of Bhutto and exploited Islamization for his own vested interest. Suleri depicts “the forced Islamization of Pakistani society under General Zia’s regime” (Kanwal, 2015, p. 24).

People filled with zeal for partition of the United India, soon lost their excitement due to internal factions which intensified during the separation of Bangladesh in 1971. Pip, father of Suleri and editor-in-chief of a leading newspaper, is an example of it in the memoir. He was a great admirer of Quaid e Azam, “He loved everything about that man: his design, his phrase, his clothes” (Suleri, 2014, p. 113). But after the partition, Pip found a different Pakistan. He was not happy with the ruling elites, whether civilian or military. He did not find the Pakistan which he dreamed of during his struggle for the partition.

After the partition of Pakistan, Pip was mostly in jail due to martial law and censorship, “So prime ministers came and went, and Pip was in and out of jail” (Suleri, 2014, p. 117). Martial law and censorship were some of the reasons which disappointed the active supporter of the partition of Pakistan, “when Pip emerged from jail and found General Ayub in charge, the parliament disbanded: it made him decide that he had had his fill of editing for a while and should look for something different” (p. 118). It is military dictatorship which has paralyzed the democratic set-up in Pakistan. Suleri (2014) highlights the overwhelming dominance of military dictators, General Ayub and General Yahya, in Pakistan (p. 120). General Ayub was the first military dictator who ruled from 1958 till 1969, “When Pip emerged from jail and found General Ayub in charge, the Parliament disbanded” (Suleri, 2014, p. 118). As a military dictator, he ruled against the wishes of the then Combined Opposition Parties which represented “a wide spectrum of public opinion” (Jalal, 2014, p. 115). This post-independent scenario confirms Fanon’s criticism of the emerging elites, military-elites in this case (2004, P.117).

In Pakistan, the problem of ethnic exploitation has emerged due to lack of harmony among various ethnic groups. The ethnic politics still prevails in the country. For instance, Pashtun ethnic group in Pakistan is marginalized by misrepresenting (by mocking) its culture and language, in short its identity, “By subjecting Pashtun heritage to erasure, the state predicates Pashtun’s inclusion in the mainstream Pakistani citizenship on the negation of their culture and language” (Taimur, 2016, p. 187). The mainstream Pakistani media portrays Pashtun as clownish people in comedic performances; they are shown as unrefined citizens who are not given respectable status in Pakistan (Taimur, 2016, p. 189)

The Pashtuns under leadership of Khan Abdul Ghaffar Khan showed their allegiance to the newly-born country, Pakistan. The *Khudai Khidmatgars* made it clear that they “regard Pakistan as their own country and pledge that they shall do their utmost to strengthen and safeguard its interest and make every sacrifice for the cause” (Marwat, 2007). However, Pashtuns have not been given a status of equality in Pakistan. They are still striving for their identity which is distorted in order to represent them as unrefined and undesirable citizens. Marginalization of Pashtun ethnic group in Pakistan is discussed in the paper to reveal the presence of ethnic politics in the country. Ethnic politics has already damaged the country in the war of 1971 which broke out due to marginalization of the East Pakistan, the Bangladesh of today.

The trauma developed during the partition, based on religious element, of the subcontinent still prevails in Pakistan. Unfortunately, leaders of Pakistan have not learnt any lesson from the separation of East Pakistan. Ethnic hatred and religious differences still prevail in the politics of the country which has disturbed national unity.

Sidhwa's novel *Ice-Candy Man* depicts religious hatred which has resulted in bloodshed during the partition of the subcontinent. The novel illuminates the trauma caused by religious identity in separating closely connected people during the days of the partition. The study of *Meatless Days* reveals failure of Pakistani nation due to overwhelming military dictatorship and division of the nation due to ethnic politics.

Conclusion

Nationalism played a key role in the movements of national liberation. However, with demise of colonialism, new problems have emerged. The religious zeal during the partition divided people of the United India in terms of faith-based identities. Religious identity could not maintain unity of Pakistani nation; people of East Pakistan separated from West Pakistan in 1971. The post-independent Pakistan has also witnessed the emergence of the ruling elite which utilizes its power and exploits people. This exploitation has created ethnic rifts and regionalism. The passion for national unity is lost due to the ethnic politics. The separation of East Pakistan (Bangladesh) is a quintessential example of the terrible impact of ethnic politics in Pakistan. The analysis of *Ice-Candy Man* unveils the problems which emerged due to division of the Indian Subcontinent on the basis of religious identity. The study of *Meatless Days* reveals pitfalls of nationalism based on ethnic identities which have led to increasing violence in Pakistan. The study of the memoir also reveals undesirable dominance and intervention of military elites in the politics of Pakistan. The political atmosphere in Pakistan is dominated by ethnic politics. Ethno-religious politics has supported the neocolonialist group which exploits people of the same nation in the name of ethnicity and religion. Pakistan needs true democratic leadership which addresses issues of its people without discrimination. The minority communities must be given equal space in the country since they are marginalized due to the religious identity. Lack of tolerance for other ethnic and religious groups is responsible for violence in Pakistan. The citizens of Pakistan should be treated equally irrespective of their ethnicity or religion.

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